

Bargīta: The Classical Music of Assam

Shirumoni Hazarika

Department of History,
Nowgong College (Autonomous), Assam

Bargita, the classical music tradition of Assam, embodies a rich cultural heritage deeply rooted in the state's history and ethos. This abstract delves into the essence of Bargīta, tracing its origins, evolution, and significance within Assamese culture. It explores the classical music forms, including Borgīta, Ojapali, and Ankia Nāt, which have been nurtured and passed down through generations. The abstract highlights the distinctive features of Bargīta, such as its devotional themes, intricate melodies, and poetic expressions, which serve as a medium for spiritual contemplation and cultural expression. Furthermore, it discusses the role of Bargīta in promoting social cohesion, preserving linguistic identity, and fostering a sense of collective belonging among the people of Assam. Through an exploration of Bargita, this abstract offers insights into the profound cultural legacy of Assam's classical music tradition and its enduring relevance in contemporary society.

Keywords: Ojapali, AnkiaNāt, cohesion, legacy.